

EFFECT OF HATHA YOGA AND AEROBIC DANCE PRACTICE ON MEMORY OF ADOLESCENT GIRLS

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ABSTRACT

Yoga is an ancient Indian Philosophy. The purpose of the study was to evaluate psychological response, to find out the changes in memory through the Yoga and aerobic dance practices. The total subjects 120 were divided into four groups and their age ranges from 12–16 years. The duration of total practice period were 6 weeks (3 days in a week for 30 minutes). Pre test and post test data were analyzed by paired ‘t’ test method. For obtaining the significant differences ANCOVA method was adopted (Garrett, 1981). The organised Yoga and aerobic dance program definitely improved their performance in memory which is selected for psychological potentialities.

Key words: Yoga, Aerobic dance, Combined and Control group, Memory.

INTRODUCTION

Yoga has a great antiquity, long tradition and is a result of thousand of years of careful and systematic exploration by the long time of sages and Yogis on the basis of their meticulous observations and personal experiences. Description of yoga is found in Rig Veda and ancient Hindu epic, Bagwat Gita. It is meant as balance and harmony of the mind and body also as skill in work. There are four basic forms of yoga: Karma yog: The yoga of action Bhakti yog: The yoga of devotion. Dynana yog: The yoga of knowledge. Raja yog: This is a system for control of the mind. The first three forms trace their origin in Bhagwat Gita. Components of Raja yog are Hatha yog, Mantra yog and Laya yog (Telang 1999). Hatha yog is thought to be the creation of the Lord Shiva and sage Patanjali is credited with propounding Hatha Yog (Wikipedia). There are further more forms of yoga as indicated in various scriptures. There are eight basic elements of yog hence also called ashtangs. They are Yam, Niyam, Asana, (Yogasan), Pranayam, Pratyahar, Dharana, Dhyan and Samadhi. Hatha Yoga Pradipika mentions Adinaath and his disciples Matsyendranath, Gorakhanath. Yoga is science of life which helps man to attain his highest potential and highest state or consciousness. It has various psychological techniques involving asanas, Pranayamas etc. The term Yoga is applied to the attainment

of highest aim, i.e. integration of personality as well as the various methods and techniques used for the fulfilment of that aim.

The ground for its introduction to the western world was laid in 1893, with the visit of Swami Vivekanand to United State of America. He gained recognition when he represented Hinduism at the world Parliament of religions in Chicago. Soon after this, the world's awareness of Indian philosophy began to grow through the work of groups such as the Theosophical Society arranged for the most of the ancient Indian philosophical texts available at that time to be translated, including the yoga sutras of Patanjali, which was interpreted by English novelist and Christopher Isherwood. Over the next few decades, the west's interest in Indian philosophy continued to grow. The teachings of J. Krishnamurty considerably widened the appeal and understanding of Vedic philosophy. With an increasing awareness of the philosophy grew an interest in the physical practice with which it was so closely linked 'yoga'. In 1935, the eminent Swiss psychologist Carl Jung described yoga as, 'one of the greatest things the human mind has ever created'.

The origin of hatha yoga developed in India. In Sanskrit, 'Ha' means 'Sun' and 'Tha' means Moon. 'Hatha' means 'forceful' implying that powerful work must be done to purify the body. Yoga means to yoke, or to join two things together, hence hatha yoga is meant to join together sun (masculine, active) energy with the moon (feminine, receptive) energy, thus producing balance and greater power in an individual. It is the branch of Yoga which concentrates on physical health and mental well being. Hatha Yoga uses bodily postures (asanas) with the goal of bringing about a sound healthy body clear, and peaceful mind.

According to physiotherapist and yoga teacher, Patel (2008), there should be no adverse effects and pain relief is possible by practice of yogasanas by various mechanisms such as relaxation of muscles or release of muscular tension; regulation of breath to increase pain tolerance; increased lubrication of joints reducing painful stiffness; improving pliability of soft tissues around joints and strengthening of antigravity mechanism for erect posture. She had applied yogas in four areas or ways: personality development, stress management, complete health, disease prevention and cure. She had presented an integrated approach of yoga which she refers as Physio-Yoga.

There are many study found increased physical function, slightly better levels of social functioning, and lower levels of sleep dysfunction and fatigue giving indications that yogasanas practice had positive effect on quality of life in this adverse and life threatening condition (Anderson, 2006). Mitra (2020) argued that hatha yoga has positive effect on vital capacity. It works to make the spine supple and to promote circulation of all organs, glands and tissues. Hatha yoga postures also stretch and align the body promoting balance and flexibility. Aerobic exercises such as aerobic dance is a fun way to get fit. It helps an individual to burn body fat. In this article, an attempt has been made to observe the improvement which occurs in the psychological health following aerobic and Yoga

practices among the adolescent. Aerobic dance and Hatha yoga have to produce improvements in psychological well being. People from all ages can be benefitted from the aerobic dance. Aerobic dance is a popular exercise among adolescent pupils.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study was as follows :

- i) To observe the impact of hatha yoga and aerobic dance practice of adolescent girls.
- ii) To find out the changes if any in memory through the following yoga and aerobic practices.

METHODOLOGY

The total subjects were one hundred and twenty (120) selected from the school of Rabindra Vidyapith High School (H.S) and age ranging from 12–16 years. All the subjects possessed sound physique. All the subjects were divided into four groups i.e. Hatha Yoga, aerobic dance, combined and control groups.

Practice Schedule

The total period of treatments was 6 weeks and each group practiced three days in a week and duration was 30 minutes which supervised exercise program for experimental subjects and control group continued usual activity. The subjects practiced the Asanas and Pranayamas.

Criteria measured

Age, height and weight were measured by school record, stadiometer and weighing machine accordingly. Memory was measured by Questionnaire method, (Shulmon,1972). Experimental subjects completed a 6-week supervised exercise program. Control subjects continued usual activity. The subjects practiced the Asanas & pranayama for 30 minutes / day & thrice a week Asanas were Tadasana, Tratayaka Chakrasana, Surja namaskar, Sarbagasana, Halasana etc. and Pranayamas were Bhastrika, Kapal bhati, Bhamari etc. Aerobic dance with music also were practiced thrice a week and 30 mins. / day. For statistical analysis, standard procedures have been adapted. Mean and SD were first computed. Then, pretest and post test data were analyzed by paired ‘t’ test method (Garrett, 1981). For obtaining the significant differences ANCOVA method (Garrett, 1981) was adopted.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

For testing the differences between mean scores selected psychological variables of Hatha Yoga Group, Aerobic Dance Group, Combined Group (Hatha Yoga and Aerobic

Dance) as Control Group of subjects. The level of significance were at 0.05 and 0.01 of confidence. The mean and SD of their personal data (age, height and weight) were recorded on table 1(a) & 1(b).

Table – 1(a)

Pre-test : (Mean \pm SD) of Yoga, aerobic dance, combined and control group variables

Yoga Gr. Mean \pm SD	Aerobic Dance Gr. Mean \pm SD	Combined Gr. Mean \pm SD	Control Gr. Mean \pm SD	
13.77 \pm 1.25	13.8 \pm 0.81	14.67 \pm 0.99	14.90 \pm 0.92	
141.70 \pm 6.10	149.37 \pm 4.43	151.3 \pm 9.08	150.30 \pm 8.54	
38.67 \pm 5.96	42.23 \pm 4.72	42.70 \pm 7.00	40.77 \pm 5.16	
Memory	27.80 \pm 4.78	29.70 \pm 4.45	27.03 \pm 5.65	27.10 \pm 4.88

Table – 1(b)

Post-test : (Mean \pm SD) of Yoga, aerobic dance, combined and control group variables

	Yoga Gr. Mean \pm SD	Aerobic Dance Gr. Mean \pm SD	Combined Gr. Mean \pm SD	Control Gr. Mean \pm SD
Personal Data				
Weight	37.13 \pm 5.48	40.20 \pm 4.24	41.70 \pm 6.22	41.33 \pm 5.40
Psychological variable				
Memory	31.40 \pm 5.16	32.67 \pm 4.73	30.17 \pm 4.29	27.53 \pm 4.73

Personal Data

The age, height and weight of the subjects had been considered as personal variable.

Age : Mean scores and standard deviation of four groups of age were 13.77 ± 1.25 , 13.8 ± 0.81 , 14.67 ± 0.99 and 14.90 ± 0.92 years respectively in Table – 1(a).

Height : Mean scores and standard deviation of four groups of height were 141.70 ± 6.10 , 149.37 ± 4.43 , 151.37 ± 9.08 and 150.30 ± 8.54 cm. respectively in Table–1(a).

Weight : Mean scores and standard deviation of four groups of weight in pre-test were 38.67 ± 5.96 , 42.23 ± 4.72 , 42.70 ± 7.00 and 40.77 ± 5.16 kg respectively in Table–1(a) and Fig. No. 1. Post test weights mean and SD were 37.13 ± 5.48 , 40.20 ± 4.24 , 41.70 ± 6.22 and 41.33 ± 5.40 kg respectively in Table No.–1(b) and Fig. 1. After completion of the training programme mean scores of weight of all experimental groups were decreased slightly.

Psychological Variable

In my study the psychological variable was memory.

Table – 2

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for memory among the four groups

	Sources of Variation	Ss	df	Ms	F
Pre Test	Between groups	139.22	3	46.41	2.07
	Within groups	2604.77	116	22.45	
	Total	2743.99	119		
Post Test	Between groups	432.09	3	144.03	5.82
	Within groups	2869.50	116		
	Total	3301.59	119		

$$F_{0.05} = 2.68, F_{0.01} = 3.96$$

F is significant at both levels in post test

Table – 3

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for memory among the groups

Source of Variation	df	SS _{X.Y}	SS _{Y.X}	MS _{Y.X} (V _{Y.X})	F _{Y.X}	SD _{Y.X}

Among Gr. Means	3	194.23	187.40	62.47	13.75	2.13
Within Gr. SS	115	2472.63	522.30	4.54		
Total	118	2666.86	709.70			

$F_{0.05} = 2.68$, $F_{0.01} = 3.96$

F is significant at both levels ($F_{0.05} = 2.68$ & $F_{0.01} = 3.96$).

Table –4

Significance of difference among adjusted Y Means of memory

Variables	SE _d	df	Diff. Adjusted Mean	Sig. at 0.05 or 0.01
Yoga vs. Aerobic dance Gr.	0.55	115	0.54	NS
Yoga vs. Combined Gr.	0.55	115	0.51	NS
Yoga vs. Control Gr.	0.55	115	3.20**	0.01
Aerobic dance vs. Combined Gr.	0.55	115	0.03	NS
Aerobic dance vs. Control Gr.	0.55	115	2.67**	0.01
Combined vs. Control Gr.	0.55	115	2.70**	0.01

*Sig. at 0.05 level, **Sig. at 0.01 level, NS is Non-significant.

From the Table No. 1(a) & 1(b) it was found that mean \pm SD of memory before training of all the groups were 27.80 ± 4.78 , 29.70 ± 4.45 , 27.03 ± 5.65 , 27.10 ± 4.88 and after training were 31.40 ± 5.16 , 32.67 ± 4.73 , 30.17 ± 4.29 , 27.53 ± 4.73 respectively.

Participating in Yoga and aerobic dance programme all the groups increased their memory [(Table No. 1(a) & 1(b))]. Since all the mean scores of memory were not equal, analysis of variance was computed (Table No. 2) to find the significant difference among the four means ANCOVA (Table No. 3) was done to find out the significant effect after participating the exercise programme groups. It is observed that the F value was significant at 0.01 level. So, treatment had positive effect on the groups. After six weeks exercise programme memory was increased (Table No. 4) in all experimental groups in compare to control group at 0.01 level of significance. In this study yoga group was better than the other groups.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of above-mentioned discussion, it can be concluded that the Hatha yoga provides evidences to indicate the importance of the connection that exists among the mind, body and spirit. More importantly, this review has revealed the significance of the mind-body-spirit connection in overall individual health status. Over time and steadfast research, yoga will continue to be assimilated with other aerobic exercise forms. Future accomplishments in yoga research would greatly influence the global community to embrace hatha yoga for its various health benefits. On the other hand, hatayoga has increased experimental group's memory significantly in comparison to other control and combined group. I can come to a conclusion that hatayoga along with aerobic dance can increase a person's memory and can enhance their various psychological potentials.

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